

MAELSTROM

MArInE Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management

D6.5

Low temperature
pyrolysis treatment(s)
of collected ML

11-03-2025

MAELSTROM

General Information

H2020 call	CE-FNR-09-2020 Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter
Grant Agreement #	101000832
Project Title	Smart technology for Marine Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management
Project Acronym	MAELSTROM
Project Duration	January 2021 – December 2024
Project Budget	6 809 461.25 Euros
Related work package	WP6
Related task(s)	T6.5
Lead Organisation	MAKEEN
Contributing Organizations	
Dissemination Level	Public

Authoring & Approval

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History of changes

Version	Date	Author	Description of changes
V0.1	20/09/2024	Anne-Sophie Høgh Mahler, Charlotte Kærsgaard Hansen, Jakob Eltzholtz, Peter Krogh Olsen, Ane Matilde Strandgaard Borgbjerg, Morten Grønbech Møller, Mathias Volsmann Simonsen, Irene Bach Velling Villadsen Dr. Gian Claudio Faussonne	First draft
V0.2	24/09/2024	Giorgio Betteto	Second draft
V0.3	30/09/2024	Irene Bach Velling Villadsen	Third draft
Final version	09/10/2024	Fantina Madricardo, Vanessa Moschino	Final Version
Revised version	11/03/2025	Fantina Madricardo, Vanessa Moschino	The Figure numbers were corrected throughout the text.

Executive Summary

It is crucial to develop technologies that can be used to collect and recycle marine litter. This is the overall focus of the project MAELSTROM. The role of MAKEEN Energy (ME) in the project was to perform low-temperature pyrolysis on the leftover plastics received from GEES, and the aim was to produce a marine diesel phase with a naphtha phase and black solid as secondary products. The produced marine diesel phase was compared with the ISO 8217-DMA standard to evaluate the quality. Furthermore, both the obtained liquids and the black solid fraction were assessed regarding uses to obtain circularity.

The marine litter received came unsorted and unwashed. At ME it was roughly sorted leaving out materials known NOT to give the required quality of ISO 8217-DMA oil and/or low yield and there of no interest for an energy consuming process. Most of the waste stream applicable for pyrolysis was PE buoys and this material was shredded and then analyzed with a NIR-scanner and then processed in MAKEENS large-scale continuous operating test plant. This results in four product streams from the pyrolysis process being MGO and naphtha (which are both liquid) syngas, and a residue of black solid powder

The produced MGO was analyzed for evaluation against ISO 8217-DMA as requested in the MAELSTROM agreement and all obtained liquids, the black solid fraction, and the gas was assessed regarding uses to obtain circularity.

Also, a subcontractor, SINTOL, performed tests on material supplied by GEES and their results are included in the report as well. The processing was performed in a small-scale setup and as batch-processing.

The material submitted to SINTOL was shredded and divided into 3 fractions, consisting of multilayer packaging, Styrofoam and Shredded/pulverized epoxy resin. Since the material delivered by GEES was not sufficient, material sourced locally such as PET bottles was added to check the effect of this type of polymer on the process. The reason for this focus relies on the behavior of PET under thermal decomposition.

The material was processed through pyrolysis, distillation, and polishing and the output liquid was assessed. Mass balance was calculated and assessed after pyrolysis, distillation, and polishing.

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1 Introduction to the MAELSTROM project

MAELSTROM is a project funded under the Topic CE-FNR-09-2020 Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter. MAELSTROM strives to provide answers and diversified solutions to the complex issues regarding the removal and sustainable treatment of marine litter legacy.

MAELSTROM contemplates the integration of complementary technologies for marine litter removal in different European coastal ecosystems, compounded with full-fledged circular economy and societal oriented solutions. In particular, the project (i) outlines a reliable multidisciplinary and scientifically sound approach for the assessment of marine debris distribution and impact on marine life in highly valuable ecosystems and protected areas; (ii) designs and manufactures scalable, replicable and automated technologies, co-powered with renewable energy and second generation fuel, to identify, remove and sort marine litter; (iii) evaluates over time the effectiveness of marine litter removal devices along with their impact on local ecosystems; (iv) integrates different technologies to track, sort and recycle all types of collected marine litter into valuable raw materials for future marketisation; (v) assesses the economic and societal impact of the MAELSTROM solutions while providing a comprehensive life-cycle assessment of the technologies and products; (vi) raises social awareness about the marine litter issue and engages citizens and stakeholders in MAELSTROM activities; (vii) interplays with similar projects to maximize innovation uptake for marine litter removal within and outside the EU.

2 MAELSTROM Consortium

The MAELSTROM project consortium consists of the following members:

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3 Aims of the Deliverable

Marine litter has become an increasing ecological problem with plastics being one of the major components. Several million tons of plastic enter the ocean each year, accumulating in the marine environment. When the plastic enters the ocean, it can be degraded over time into smaller pieces which can be harmful when ingested by living organisms including humans (Thomson et al. 2024). Therefore, it is crucial to develop technologies that can be used to collect and recycle marine litter. This is the overall focus of the project MAELSTROM. The different partners have different focuses in the process chain from the collection and sorting of marine litter to recycling technologies from which products with meaningful purposes can be obtained. MAKEEN Power do no longer exist and therefore, the project has been continued by MAKEEN Energy (in short: ME).

The role of MAKEEN Energy (ME) in the MAELSTROM project is to perform low-temperature pyrolysis on the leftover plastics received from GEES as described in WT6.5 and WT6.6. To sum up these two sections, the aim is to produce a marine diesel phase with a naphtha phase and black solid as secondary products. The produced marine diesel phase will be compared with the ISO 8217-DMA standard to evaluate the quality. Furthermore, both the obtained liquids and the black solid fraction will be assessed regarding uses to obtain circularity. The pyrolysis will be performed on an advanced and large-scale continuous process pyrolysis test setup located at the ME facility

The marGnet pyrolysis plant mentioned in WT6.5 and WT6.6 is not located at ME but at SINTOL. SINTOL will therefore also receive marine litter and will process it using the marGnet prototype following the same procedures followed during the marGnet project. Produced fuels/energy carriers will be shipped to GEES to accomplish the assigned task.

In Figure 1, the flow diagram of the Maelstrom Recycling System (MRS) can be seen. In the MRS, ML is collected and sorted into different materials streams hereunder a metal stream and a plastic stream. The aim is, that the plastic not suited for mechanical recycle can be processed via low-temperature pyrolysis to produce MGO.

Figure 1: Maelstrom Recycling System 1

4 Processing at MAKEEN ENERGY

4.1 Preprocessing of Marine Litter - MAKEEN

The received material from GEES was intact collected raw marine litter (ML) which had not been washed and dried prior to shipping nor sorted in any way. It consisted of a wide range of materials including fishing net, rope, tires, expanded polystyrene, inflatable rubber animals, cans, syringes, lighters, wood, plastic chairs, buoys, plastic toys, shoes, bottles, and mussels. Pictures of the raw material can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Marine Litter from GEES: 1) fishing nets and rope, 2) inflatable rubber animals, 3) mixed metallic litter, 4) buoys, 5) wood, 6) mixed plastic litter, 7) PET bottles and Styrofoam, and 8) mussel covered buoys.

A preliminary sorting was performed removing non-plastic materials such as wood, metals, textiles, and most of the mussels from the ML, since this is not part of MPs inlet material in the MRS as seen in Figure 1. The tires were also removed since already existing recycle techniques for tires are present. This includes Imdex A/S (DK), who produce rubber granulate from used tires for different applications, and Pyrum Innovations AG (D), who are specialized in performing pyrolysis on rubber material. Also, studies at MP on pyrolysis of tires have shown critical contamination consequences for equipment and products, while tires and other rubbers have shown to result in low oil yield by Faussonne et al. (Faussonne et al., 2021) (Faussonne et al., 2021).

After the preliminary sorting every fragment was analyzed by Near-Infrared (NIR) scanning, as seen in Figure 3, to determine the type of plastics and thereby defining the inlet stream of the pyrolysis process. The fragments being PET, PVC or nondetectable fragments was removed. The sorting was therefore only based on the type of plastic and not the application of the given product. Some of the fishing nets were removed because they could not be analyzed, however fishing nets can be recycled in other ways. The companies Plastix (DK) and Redivivus Polymers APS (DK) both convert used fishing nets via mechanical and thermal treatments to plastic pellets for use in other industries. Furthermore, Faussonne et. al has investigated pyrolysis of fishing nets, which resulted in low oil yields (Faussonne et al., 2021).

Figure 3: Near-Infrared scanning of marine litter.

Figure 4: The discarded material based on the Near-Infrared scanning method

PET was removed based on knowledge from the Plastcon project where PET has shown clogging tendencies on the system. In addition to this, mechanical recycling of PET is being performed industrially which is preferred compared to chemical recycling. Furthermore, studies show a direct correlation between the amount of PET and increase in solid product formation meaning lower oil yield (Genuino et al., 2023). PVC was removed as it results in low oil yields and as it degrades into hydrochloric acid which corrodes the process equipment (Anuar Sharuddin et al., 2016). The removal of PET and PVC included bottles, some shoes, and inflatable rubber animals. The smaller fragments PET and PVC, which was removed, can be seen in Figure 5. This meant that most of the waste stream applicable for pyrolysis was PE buoys as seen on 4) in Figure 2.

From the MRS, the intension was to remove polyolefins including PP and PE, but also PET and PS to be mechanically reused and produce pellets sold as “certified Marine plastics”. The remaining non-recyclable products should then be processed by MP by low-temperature pyrolysis. But since marine diesel cannot be produced from the remaining non-recyclable products only, PE was not removed from the received material. PE material is known to be easily pyrolyzed in the Plastcon plant and cause high yields of oil. It is a good input material to produce oil, which resembles marine diesel.

The recycling of plastic can be divided into primary (re-extrusion), secondary (mechanical) and tertiary (chemical) recycling (Căta et al., 2015). Mechanical recycling is a common and effective method for plastic reuse, but the physical and chemical properties of the polymer will deteriorate during each cycle due to a decrease in molecular weight. Eventually, the polymer is degraded or mixed with other plastic types and the plastic is landfilled or incinerated after use. To avoid landfill of the plastic, a thermochemical recovery method can be used such as pyrolysis.

Figure 5: Shredded Marine litter.

Figure 6: Sample preparation setup with the wedge of plastic in the background and the drum in from. The sample shown is not ML.

Post sorting, the material needed to be fragmented into smaller units before pyrolysis. The biggest units were cut into approximately 40 x 15 cm pieces with a bayonet saw. Afterwards, the material was shredded into 10 x 10 mm pieces to ensure better heat transfer during the pyrolysis process. The shredded ML can be seen in Figure 5. To get a representative sample from the shredded material the shredded ML was placed on the floor in a wedge. A sample of 2 L was taken 5 places on each side of the wedge

and 5 places on the top resulting in 30L total. This was mixed in a drum and transferred through a riffle splitter until a volume of 1 L was obtained. The sample preparation and equipment can be seen in Figure 6. The homogenized and representative sample was analyzed by NIR scanning, and the result is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: NIR scanning of a representative sample of marine litter.

The scan shows a majority of PE represented in yellow with low-density PE represented in black while the other plastic types are present in percentages below 1%.

4.2 Pyrolysis process - MAKEEN

When performing low-temperature pyrolysis, the material is heated to approximately 400°C in an oxygen-free reactor. This leads to the degradation of chemical bonds resulting in smaller polymeric molecules in the vapour phase. The vapour phase can be split into three fractions using a condenser system, resulting in two liquid phases and a gaseous phase. This results in four product streams from the pyrolysis process being MGO and naphtha, which are both liquid, syngas that can be burned, and a residue of black solid powder. It is important to note that the quality and quantity of the liquid products highly depends on the chemical composition and quality of the input material.

The low temperature pyrolysis of ML was performed on the already existing Plastcon equipment. A flowchart of the process is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Flowchart of the pyrolysis process of Marine Litter.

First the shredded material was fed into an extruder at a rate of appr. 25 kg/h, where it was preheated and meanwhile densified. The densified material then entered the electrically heated reactor with a volume of 1000L. Nitrogen was flushed through the system during the pyrolysis process to keep an inert environment. The produced vapours left the reactor and entered a second reactor operating at a lower temperature where gasses with boiling point above this temperature condensed. To split the vapour fraction into MGO and naphtha two sets of condensers were used. The two oil fractions were collected in separate tanks, while the residual black solid was collected from the first reactor and the syngas was sent to a flare. The collected MGO fraction is seen in Figure 9.

Figure 9: MGO fraction before distillation

The produced MGO appeared cloudy and not clear and bright, as described in the ISO 8217. This was also expected as pyrolysis on PE is known to yield a cloudy and waxy oil (Shin et al., 2011). Therefore, the MGO was further refined using distillation where MGO was obtained at temperatures between 170°C and 300°C.

4.3 Mass balance - MAKEEN

In the performed experiment 230 kg of ML was processed without any operational challenges. The produced oil was distilled which resulted in the product distribution seen in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Product distribution from the pyrolysis and distillation.

The liquid phases, MGO and naphtha, accounts for around 53% of the product based on mass with the MGO being the smallest fraction. The yield of the MGO fraction from the process was relatively low being 17.1%, which is less than 30% of the total yield of liquid produced. The 2.6% black solid is a residual product after the pyrolysis while the fraction of 10.2% covering other residue is the highly viscous part of the oil, that was left after the distillation. The yield of the produced gas was 26.2%. During the process 8.1% was lost which can be due to both loss of mass in the equipment, when handling the products or to uncertainties in the process.

The total yield of pyrolysis oil from the pyrolysis process was around 63% which corresponds with the findings of Faussone et. al who performed pyrolysis on ML including fishing nets and obtained an oil yield between 42.0% and 63.3% (Faussone

et al., 2021). Das and Tiwari have performed pyrolysis on both virgin LDPE and virgin HDPE and obtained yields around 83%, which was more compared to using ML as input material (Das & Tiwari, 2018). They also observed lower black solid yields of around 0.5% and gas yields of around 17%. These differences can be due to the purity of the plastic used. Virgin plastics are highly pure plastics while the ML can contain different types of unknown additives and have impurities on the surface such as sand and mussels.

4.4 Analysis of products - MAKEEN

4.4.1 Liquid

The distilled liquid products of MGO and naphtha can be seen in Figure 11. The MGO on the left has a clear appearance with an orange and brown color. The naphtha also appears clear and bright but with a yellow color. Since the naphtha in the context of the project is a by-product, the naphtha has not been analyzed further.

Figure 11: The two oil fractions where MGO is on the left and naphtha is on the right.

The produced and purified MGO was analyzed following the ISO-8217 – DMA standard for MGO. This includes the characteristics presented in Table 1.

Table 1: ISO 8217 – DMA product characteristics.

Properties	
Viscosity at 40 °C	Lubricity corrected WSD at 60 °C
Density at 15 °C	Cloud point
Cetane Index	Cold filter plugging point
Sulfur content	Pour point (winter/summer)
Flash point	Appearance

Hydrogen sulfide	Water content
Acid number	Ash content
Oxidation stability	Carbon residue

Some of the properties could not be analyzed by the analysis laboratory and therefore specific analyses were chosen to evaluate the quality of the obtained MGO. The non performed analyses are oxidation stability, cloud point and cold filter plugging point. Since the oxidation stability must be measured within short time of the test this analysis could not be done due to transportation time to the analysis laboratory. To stabilize the sample, antioxidant was added. Cloud point and cold filter plugging point has no requirements from the ISO 8217 – DMA and thereby no limiting values. The results of the tests must only be reported and would therefore not have contributed to the evaluation of the produced MGO for Maelstrom. The appearance must be clear and bright according to the standard. This has been evaluated on site by MAKEEN Energy, which is also the case for the measurement of the flash point.

An additional analysis of chlorine content has been added since it was considered relevant. The ISO 8217-DMA MGO standard is made for fossil based MGO where chlorines are not an issue, but since the plastic from the sea might have absorbed or reacted with the chlorine in the water, the chlorine content was measured. The presence of chlorides in the MGO is crucial as organic chlorides can decompose to hydrochloric acid, leading to corrosion and damage of the fuel system equipment (Mitra et al., 2022).

In Table 2 the results from the performed analyses can be seen. The flash point measurement was performed in-house, while the other analysis was carried out by FORCE Technology or Intertek.

Table 2: Results from the analysis carried out on the produced MGO presented alongside the requirements, the test method, and an evaluation of whether requirements are met.

Analysis	Result	Standard requirements		Testing method	Requirement met?
		Min	Max		
Viscosity 40°C [mm ² /s]	1.923	2.000	6.000	DS/EN ISO 3104:2020	No
Density 15°C [g/ml]	0.799	-	0.8900	ISO 12185	Yes
Cetane Index [-]	62.8	40	-	ISO 4264	Yes
Sulfur content [% w/w]	0.024	-	1.00	DS/EN ISO 16994 A (2016)	Yes
Flash point [°C]	71.5	60.0	-	Tested at ME	Yes
H ₂ S content [mg/kg]	>1	-	2.00		Yes
Acid number [mg KOH/g]	0.53	-	0.5	M2.025 based on ISO 660:2020	No
Carbon residue [% w/w]	<0.1	-	0.30	TGA	Yes
Pour point [°C]	-21°C	-	-6/0	ISO 3016	Yes
Appearance	Clear	Clear and Bright			Yes
Water content [% w/w]	0.004	-	-	ASTM D6304 (2020), procedure B	Yes
Ash content [% w/w]	0.001	-	0.010	ISO 6245	Yes
Lubricity corrected WSD 60°C [µm]	<200	-	520	ISO 12156	Yes
Cl content [% w/w]	0.003	-	-	DS/EN ISO 16994 A (2016)	-

From Table 2 all values fulfill the requirements except from the acid number of 0.53 mg KOH/g and the viscosity of 1.923 mm²/s. If these deviations are not tolerable, different approaches can be taken to adjust the properties. The acid number can be lowered by using neutralizing additives containing alkaline chemicals and catalysts (Mohd Shohaimi, 2013), while the viscosity can be increased by adding a thickening agent.

No exact limit of the chlorine content was found but indications of 50 mg/kg was found (*CIMAC Working Group Fuels-WG7*, 2022). In %w/w this correlate to 0.00005% w/w meaning a great exceed of the found limit value is found in the MGO. To lower the chlorine content either a pretreatment or post-treatment must be performed. A dry

dichlorination could be performed using alkaline adsorbents prior to the pyrolysis process (Chen & Tsai, 2022). Another solution is thermal dichlorination by using flue gas instead of nitrogen as gas flow during pyrolysis (Han et al., 2023).

The produced naphtha fraction was not analyzed, but it likely consists of short hydrocarbons with low boiling points. The uses of naphtha depend on the chemical composition, but it can be purified and used as a chemical feedstock to produce new plastic, it can be used as precursors to fuel products or as solvent in different chemical industries (Dai et al., 2021; Speight & El-Gendy, 2018).

4.4.2 Gas

The chemical composition of the gas can be seen in Table 3 where the gas species and its corresponding relative content in weight percentages is showed. The total relative content is 99.26% meaning that nonmentioned gas species are present in the gas but at low concentration.

Table 3: Components in the gas and the gas composition.

Gas species	Relative content [% w/w]
Water vapor	4.61
Carbon monoxide (CO)	0.30
Sulfur dioxide (SO ₂)	0.10
Hydrogen chloride (HCl)	0.44
Methane (CH ₄)	15.37
Ethane (C ₂ H ₆)	16.95
Propane (C ₃ H ₈)	2.18
Butane (C ₄ H ₁₀)	6.19
Heptane (C ₇ H ₁₆)	1.84
Octane (C ₈ H ₁₈)	1.67
Ethylene (C ₂ H ₄)	14.30
Propene (C ₃ H ₆)	21.25
1-Pentene (C ₅ H ₁₀)	12.61
Isopentene (C ₅ H ₁₀)	1.45
Total	99.26

The Table shows that the most prevalent gas species are the short hydrocarbon chains from C1 to C5 chains, while the longer hydrocarbon chains from C6 to C8 appears in lower concentrations. This makes sense since the longer and thereby heavier chains are condensed during the process and present in the oil. Apart from the carbon chains 4.61% water vapor is seen, which is good since the water is

unwanted in the MGO. This correlates with the low water content in the MGO oil. Furthermore, carbon monoxide, sulfur dioxide and hydrogen chloride are present in the gas but in low concentrations. These components are undesired air pollutants with health concerns and/or environmental disruption. Carbon monoxide is considered toxic as it disrupts the oxygen uptake in the body (WHO, n.d.). Sulfur dioxides are also considered toxic as it contributes to respiratory illness and inhibit plant growth (Minnesota Pollution Control Agency, n.d.). Lastly, when hydrogen chloride gas reacts with water vapor it produces hydrochloric acid which is highly corrosive and causes eye irritation and respiratory illness if inhaled (Merck, 2023). These components must therefore be kept at a minimum.

In the pyrolysis process the gas is a biproduct which must be disposed in the best possible way to establish the oil production. The high content of small hydrocarbon chains makes the gas applicable for energy extraction. The best scenario is to utilize the gas into producing electricity to run the pyrolysis plant, which favors circularity of the gas and reduces electricity costs. A solution could be either a gas motor or gas turbine, which have an electrical efficiency of 30-40% and 40% respectively. Though the technology of a gas motor requires a certain gas quality expressed by methane number to avoid engine knocking/detonation, while the gas turbine requires a certain constant pressure. Major obstacles for the technologies are varying gas compositions while energy and CO₂ taxes interferes with the business model making the solution less favorable. Instead, the low technology solution of a kettle can be used, which is a known technology in natural gas and biogas plants. This will not produce electricity, but the gas will be disposed, and heat extracted. Depending on the local boundary conditions the heat might be sold or added to the district heating network.

4.4.3 Solids

In Figure 12 a flask with black carbon is shown. This is the solid residue of the process and constitute of 3% of the total product stream.

Figure 12: Residual black solid from the pyrolysis process.

The black solid produced from ML has not been analyzed, but previous analysis performed on black solid from the Plastcon project showed that the black solid consisted of between 40% and 55% ash. This indicates that the black solid contains high amounts of inorganic substances such as metallic compounds. In plastic production metallic compounds are used to obtain a specific functionality and appearance. They are used as colorants such as iron oxide and titanium oxide. Other metallic compounds can also be used as nucleation agents to make transparent plastics and as antioxidants to increase the robustness and lifetime of the plastic. Other types of inorganic substances that adds to the high ash content can be fillers and reinforcements in the plastics such as glass fibers (Selke et al., n.d.).

From the previous analysis it was also seen that the black solid contained between 30% and 50% carbon. Compared to Carbon Black, which the produced black solid visually resembles, the carbon content is higher as Carbon Black has a carbon content of more than 97% (Wypych & Pionteck, n.d.). Carbon Black is used as a colorant or conductivity enhancer in different industrial products (Wypych & Pionteck, n.d.), but as the produced black solid does not chemically resemble Carbon Black, the same uses are not possible. The low carbon content could also hinder the use of the produced black solid as a fuel product. However, it could be discarded by combustion in a cogeneration plant. Another possible usage of the black solid could be as filler in asphalt for construction of roads.

4.5 Product validation - MAKEEN

The final product of MGO from pyrolysis of ML followed by distillation fulfills the requirements of ISO 8217 - DMA standard to a great extent. The only concerns include the chlorine content and the slightly exceeding acid number. Though, with a total yield of 17% the MGO corresponds to less than half the yield of naphtha. It can be

discussed whether the pyrolysis of ML is feasible for the MGO production, but it must be considered that ML is a waste material that otherwise would have been incinerated or left as ocean pollution. In this way the pyrolysis of ML directly participates to the removal of plastic from the oceans and utilize the carbon from the plastic in a valuable product rather than incinerating it and releasing the carbon into the atmosphere. By transforming the ML into fuel, pyrolysis becomes a profitable solution that achieves emission reductions compared to incineration while also yielding a valuable product.

Because of the elaborate sorting of the ML the amount of actual pyrolysis input material is limited. The fact that most aliphatic plastics are supposed to be removed (see "Figure 7 MAELSTROM Recycling system and derived products" the MAELSTROM agreement: A flow chart defining sorting and recycling routes for the different ML materials) from the input stream, the quality of MGO would drop drastically. This means that the amount and the quality of the input material are too low to be processed alone. In the case of only processing ML into MGO, and following the proximity principle, small plants would be needed to process all ML close to the area where it is collected. This would result in multiple small plants distributed around Europe, which would result in the cost of the plants exceeding value of the outcome. Instead, a big plant could be used, where the amount of processed material could create a cost-effective business model. However, this would require the transportation of all ML in Europe to the one plant which is contradictive to the aim of a CO₂ reducing process. Instead of only processing ML, an alternative would be to incorporate the ML in the input stream of an already existing pyrolysis plant processing post-consumer plastic. In this case the product would not be a standardized MGO but a pyrolysis oil without certain specifications. Here the amount of ML added to the input stream of aliphatic plastic types, which yield better quality pyrolysis oil, can be adjusted. This would result in a dilution of the impurities and low-quality oil extracted from the ML. This pyrolysis oil would need to be post-processed to purify the oil and extract the valuable products of interest. Depending on the post-process conditions either fuels such as MGO or molecules suitable for use in the chemical industry can be produced from the pyrolysis oil. These purified molecules can be used as platform chemicals and solvents or to produce new plastics and pharmaceuticals.

The production of MGO or pyrolysis oil from ML will not be able to compete economically with the fossil based MGO. With the collection of plastic from the ocean, the transportation, the energy consumption of pyrolysis, and the post-process refining steps, the MGO will be much more expensive to produce than the residue

product from crude oil. On the contrary the ML based MGO or pyrolysis oil are environmentally beneficial and might be able to become certified according to different green and environmental certificates. By tracing the MGO or other products produced from the pyrolysis oil back to the ML the fuel or products could get a traceability certificate that ensures that it is produced from ML. This would require documentation from the collection of ML in the ocean throughout the world, the transportation, the sorting, the shredding, and the pyrolysis. In that way the MGO could be sold as a green fuel or a green additive to the fossil based MGO. The traceability of the ML throughout the process will likewise increase the value of other products made from the pyrolysis oil. This means that the consumers will be able to read on the product that it contains ML collected from a certain area or that their product is shipped by green MGO based transport. By tracing and certifying the products the price of the products will increase and counterbalance the more expensive production process.

In Table 4 examples of possible different certificates are listed with an explanation of the certificate's focus and requirements.

Table 4: List of relevant certificates.

Certificate/Standard	Focus / Requirements
Verra standard ^a	A project collecting and/or recycling plastics can be registered within Verra's plastic waste reduction program, that issues Plastic Credit which can be sold to finance the project.
EcoVadis ^b	EcoVadis medals recognize companies that address sustainability criteria of the themes Environment, Ethics, Labor and Human Rights, and Sustainable Procurement.
Green Circle Certified ^c	The closed loop product certification certifies a product from a company that can provide a consistent closed loop system for recycling of end-of-life product material into a new, similar, or equal value product.
EUCertPlast ^d	Certification of recyclers that treats postconsumer plastics with respect towards the environment. It ensures traceability along the whole supply chain and quality of the final product.

^a(VERRA, 2021) ^b(EcoVadis, n.d.) ^c(GreenCircle Certificate, 2023) ^d(EuCertPlast, n.d.)

If considering applying for the Verra certificate the Maelstrom project would become a part of the Plastic Waste Reduction Program. The project will be assessed to

determine the extent of plastic waste reduction and based on this the program will issue the so-called Plastic Credit to the project. The Plastic Crediting mechanism is used as a mean to finance projects that reduce plastic in the environment. The Plastic Credit can be sold to companies that want to reduce their plastic footprint in their operation by financing plastic reducing projects like Maelstrom.

Unlike Verra, the EcoVadis certificate assesses a company according to the sustainability criteria regarding Environment, Ethics, Labor and Human Rights, and Sustainable Procurement. The company, in this case MAKEEN Energy, might be acknowledged with a medal of either bronze, silver, gold or platinum that describe their sustainability management performance according to the four criteria, but only relative to other assessed companies across EcoVadis database.

In case of The Green Circle Certificate the assessment lies on the product, in this case the pyrolysis oil. The product is validated as a closed loop product utilizing life cycle thinking by recycling at the end-of-life typically into the same or similar quality product. In the Maelstrom the loop starts with the collected ML which is transformed into pyrolysis oil and lastly potentially made into new plastic. If the product of the ML is MGO the product is not a closed loop product thus it is not possible to gain the certificate.

The focus of EuCertPlast lies on the recycling process in this case the pyrolysis process, which must be capable of recycling both pre- and post-consumer plastic waste. This certification can only be granted if the ML is recycled into new virgin plastic or other raw material for manufacturing purposes and not if the product is fuels such as MGO. The certification values the traceability of the plastic throughout the entire recycling process and supply chain. It also values calculation of the recycled content in the end-product.

Though if considering the ML only being a small part of the input stream of a pyrolysis plant processing postconsumer plastic the green certificate must be reconsidered. Especially whether the ML can be traced when mixed with other material and if the amount is sufficient to make the product a green product.

4.6 Conclusion - MAKEEN

Marine litter (ML) is a huge problem for the marine environment in all parts of the world. To solve this problem, pyrolysis has been investigated as a recycling method of ML. From the pyrolysis of ML primarily composed of PE followed by distillation an MGO product was obtained. The product was analyzed following the standard ISO 8217 – DMA for MGO, from which it can be concluded, that it fulfilled 11 out of the 13

measured requirements. The measured acid number was slightly higher than the upper limit, the viscosity measured at 40°C was slightly lower than the lower limit, while the results showed a higher amount of chlorine than what can be accepted for fossil based MGO. However, these values can be modified by different posttreatments. The yield of the produced MGO after distillation was found to be 17.1% w/w, where the total amount of liquid produced constitutes of 63% w/w. This means that the produced MGO is less than 30% w/w of the total liquid yield, which together with the need for further posttreatments indicates that producing MGO from ML is not economically feasible. Another approach could be to not produce a MGO and naphtha but to keep it in one fraction as pyrolysis oil. This can either be incorporated in the petroleum industry or be purified and used in the chemical industry as precursors to new plastic products or as solvents. Depending on which of the approaches is chosen, different certificates can be applied for, to visualize the environmental benefits of the product.

5 Processing at SINTOL

The marGnet prototype mentioned in the contract is located and SINTOL. To also perform tests in the marGnet prototype and to public demonstrate pyrolysis, SINTOL was a subcontractor to MEand Marine Litter was processed in this, operated and documented by SINTOL. The results were documented in a report submitted to ME and this chapter is a substract of this report.

The processing at SINTOL followed the same procedures followed during the marGnet project. Further details on the procedure followed can be found in the following publication: "Faussonne, G.C.; Kržan, A.; Grilc, M. Conversion of Marine Litter from Venice Lagoon into Marine Fuels via Thermochemical Route: The Overview of Products, Their Yield, Quality and Environmental Impact. Sustainability 2021, 13, 9481. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13169481>"

5.1 Preprocessing - SINTOL

Material was submitted to SINTOL by GEES RECYCLING and came already shredded.

A total of 123 Kg of material divided into 3 fractions was received:

1. Plastic film, probably multilayer packaging, approx. 5 kg;
2. Styrofoam, shredded, diameter of pieces < 1 cm, approx. 15 kg;
3. Shredded/pulverized material which was later identified by GEES as epoxy resin from boat crushing, approx. 103 kg;

Figure 13: SINTOL experimental setup – sketch.

Since the material delivered by GEES (123 Kg) was not sufficient to meet the 200 Kg target, on February 28th it was agreed with MAKEEN to include also other material sourced locally such as PET bottles (approximately 80 Kg) to check the effect of this type of polymer on the process¹. The reason for this focus relies on the behavior of PET under thermal decomposition

5.2 Pyrolysis process – SINTOL

The material was firstly converted into liquid form by mean of pyrolysis. Each pyrolysis cycle was set to 4 hours from reactor load to product collection. For Each trial 1 Kg of calcium hydroxide was added to the material to reproduce the same conditions already explored during marGnet project.

Collected pyrolysis oil from each material/trial was homogenized and distilled into 2 fractions:

- 1T, distilling from ambient temperature up to 170°C
- 2T, distilling from 170 to 320 °C

320°C was the limit temperature since no evolving vapors were collected above this threshold.

Distillates were cleaned by means of silica gel filtration and final products collected in plastic tanks. Products from PET pyrolysis, being very low in quantity, were partially added to the pyrolysis oil and partially were analyzed separately.

Experimental set up is illustrated in figure 13 is “fuel 1”, while 2T is “fuel 2” in figure respectively.

Figure 14: SINTOL experimental setup, is a picture of the experimental unit used for tests.

5.3 Mass balance - SINTOL

The feedstocks delivered by GEES and PET were processed individually to collect specific data on oil yield. A total of 32 pyrolysis cycles were performed. Six cleaning cycles (steam cleaning) were also performed when considered necessary to clean the reactor between feedstock types and to prevent fouling and clogging.

Table 5: Mass balance pyrolysis

Material	Average yield (%)		
	Solid	Liquid*	Gas
Film	40,00	5,71	54,29
Foam	22,91	48,33	28,76
Epoxy	51,05	25,42	23,53
PET	31,34	24,68	43,98
*Include water			

From the mass balance (Table 5) it is evident that both film and epoxy resin are not good candidates for conversion. Solid residue was very high in both cases being 40% and 51% for film and epoxy respectively, and the amount of produced gas is more than half the product's yield for film (>54%).

Liquid product from epoxy contained large amount of water. Water was up to 60% of the total liquid produced (included the water collected along distillation) and was separated by sedimentation. Assessing the precise quantity of produced water was not possible since water/pyrolysis oil formed an emulsion which was not easily identified.

With respect to PET, liquid was composed almost entirely by water and actual oil yield was therefore still very low (total products, including produced wax, was approx. 20 wt%, pyrolysis oil only approx. 2wt%). However, also solid products such as terephthalic acid (TPA) and wax were obtained and recovered inside the equipment. TPA can potentially be converted into light hydrocarbons by decarboxylation using a catalyst or a sorbent.

Solid residue from PET might deserve better investigation since its specific surface and structure suggest potential for graphitization and hence the manufacture of high-capacity graphite electrodes used in electric arc furnaces. This topic is however out of the scope of this report and not discussed here.

As said, the produced pyrolysis oil contained large amount of water, but it was not always easily recognizable. Probably the easily recognizable water is moisture, while chemical water is produced during pyrolysis. Water was partially separated prior to distillation, when possible, but significant amount of water was collected along with distillation. Probably water and pyrolysis oil form an emulsion which breaks only upon secondary heating during the distillation process. Worth noticing that water was collected along with 1T, being the boiling point of water below the threshold upper temperature of 1T boiling range, and easily segregated. Approximately 50% of the liquid product collected as 1T was water.

Similar results were found during marGnet project when fishing nets were processed. In this case, however, from our knowledge, no polyamides were present in the feedstock. Epoxy resin was the largest sample processed, and polyesters is probably the polymer present in this feedstock. As reported elsewhere, epoxyresins give oil yield in the order of 20-30 wt%². These figures are in line with the results obtained in our tests.

5.3.1 Distillation - SINTOL

The pyrolysis oil was homogenized and distilled. 5 cycles of distillation were performed

Since the amount of water was consistent in the liquid phase, the distillation temperature followed a flat profile due to the coexistence in evolving vapor phase of water and hydrocarbons. This is typical of the steam-distillation procedure. The

advantage of steam-distillation over simple distillation is to keep distillation temperature always below 99°C also for the hydrocarbons boiling above that temperature (thus avoiding secondary cracking reactions), but because the exact amount of water was unknown, it was not possible to perform precise separation between 1T and 2T because the effect of water on temperature mitigation ends when water is boiled off completely from the mixture. Besides, in this present case the steam-distillation was not the chosen procedure, but it was rather accidentally performed due to presence of oil-water emulsion.

For this study, however, the target 2T which has a boiling range beginning well above the 100°C, was not particularly affected.

Mass balance for distillation is reported in Table 6, Figure 16 shows the products of distillation before polishing with silica gel.

Table 6: Distillation yield

Distillation yield			
1T	2T	lost	water
%			
32,6	29,7	10,2	27,6
Kg			
12,0	11,1	3,7	10,2

PET-derived pyrolysis oil was distilled separately. Products are largely composed by water, a light hydrocarbon blend composed by BTX, benzil-benzoate and short chain alkenes and a heavy fraction of hydrocarbon (wax) distilling above 350°C. The hydrocarbon fraction, being very little in quantity, was added to the 1T fraction being almost completely aromatics. TPA acid and other crystals collected in the pipes, equipment walls, etc. was sent to the National Institute of Chemistry of Ljubljana for further investigation. Wax was partially evaluated by mean of destructive tests as solid fuel replacement but without success. Water was purified by means of deep oxidation (H₂O₂ treatment) and disposed.

Figure 15: Distillation of pyrolysis oil

Figure 16: Products of distillation

5.3.2 Polishing - SINTOL

Distillates were polished with silica gel to remove polar molecules responsible for high acidity and brown color following the procedure also employed during marGnet project. We found out that polar compounds can be effectively removed from the oil exploiting their affinity with the polar sorbent. However, the shortcoming of this approach is the liquid retention of the sorbent which causes the loss of useful product within the spent sorbent.

In fact, polishing was not as simple as originally planned. Oil retention in silica gel was found to be very high and for the 2T fraction, washing and dilution with conventional diesel fuel was made necessary to reduce the viscosity and the liquid retention of the sorbent (leaching approach). Approximately 3 L of conventional diesel were used as leaching agent to recover the 2T retained by the silica gel. Unfortunately, the use of conventional diesel as leaching agent also led the final product to be a blend between 2T produced during the experiments and conventional diesel itself. Approximately 3 L of 2T distillate were thus lost in silica gel matrix and likely replaced by conventional diesel fuel.

PP filter media, 0.5 μm , was used to separate silica gel from the oils with the help of manual operation. A closer look to the polished product is impressive: the color is clear and bright. From the visual appearance of silica gel after polishing, it is clear that the distillates are very rich in polar compounds, making their upgrading to standardized fuels a great challenge at least in large scale perspective: in fact, large amount of silica gel was used for polishing (approximately in the ratio of 0.5 kg silica

per kg of distillate), resulting in partial loss of product (especially 2T due to greater affinity with the sorbent), but on the other hand the possibility to enhance chemical properties and visual appearance of the distillates is proven. Further investigation on the silica gel regeneration is envisaged. Due to inherent instability of the distillates (no stabilizers were employed after the process), color of distillates is likely to become darker over time. This can be considered normal without affecting chemical properties of fuels

Figure 17: 2T impregnated with silica gel

Figure 18: Pouring 2T liquid after silica gel polishing

Figure 19: Silica gel liquid retention on 2T

Figure 20: Filtered distillates after polishing

5.3.3 Focus on PET pyrolysis – SINTOL

Presence of polyethylene terephthalate (PET) in the waste plastic is often problematic during pyrolysis because PET decomposes into sublimating terephthalic (TPA) and benzoic acids (BA) which cause corrosion and blockage in the processing facilities (Yoshioka et al., 2004; Artetxe et al. 2010). This was also observed in our experiments. Besides, PET pyrolysis leads to a high yield of gas fraction, a low amount of liquids, and significant yield of solid char fraction, all detrimental to fuel synthesis. On the other hand, previous experiments show that from pyrolysis of PET containing waste, aromatic hydrocarbons, namely benzene, toluene and xylene (BTX) can be produced (Blazsó, 2006). BTX market share in 2018 exceeded 162 GUSD¹ therefore research is currently ongoing to produce valuable aromatics from waste feedstocks (Chao et al., 2010, Sarker et al., 2011). When it comes to fuels production, presence of TPA and BA is detrimental to total acid number which must be below a certain level: 0.5 mgKOH/g for marine fuels for example.

If sufficient grade of decarboxylation of TPA is attained, great amount of BTX and low acidity fuels can be produced at the same time by processing mixed plastic waste and ML via pyrolysis. Ca (OH)₂ is suitable candidate for this purpose because it is cheap, safe and readily available.

Mechanism of thermal degradation of PET is similar of that of simple ester pyrolysis, where it decomposes to give olefins and acids. As reported in literature, decomposition reactions of simple esters are homogeneous, follow first order kinetics in both the vapor and liquid phase and are not affected by radical scavengers. Activation energy for ester pyrolysis was found to be 167 Kj/mol vs. a theoretical pure chain scission of the ester link of nearly 251 Kj/mol and the reaction rate constant @ 282 °C in the range of 0.2- 3.5 h⁻¹ *10³ 10. Because thermal degradation of PET produces large amount of TPA and BA other research have investigated the possibility to produce valuable chemicals by its decomposition. Masuda et al. report that the sublimate materials from PET decomposition were successfully decomposed using FeOOH catalysts in steam atmosphere at 500°C. They suggest that by the hydrolysis of PET, large amount of TPA is formed with little carbon residue (<1%), then the TPA is decomposed to carbon dioxide and benzoic acid. BA undergoes further reaction to produce acetophenone and carbon dioxide. Some acetophenone is converted to benzene and phenol. Hence, from PET decomposition, authors report a product yield

¹ <https://www.reportsanddata.com/press-release/global-btx-benzene-toluene-and-xylene-market>

- Amount of water was significant affecting the distillation profile.
- Liquid retention of silica gel was significant, particularly for 2T. Conventional diesel was used as
- leaching agent to recover 2T from silica gel. Approximately 3 L of 2T were thus lost in silica gel
- matrix and likely replaced by conventional diesel fuel.
- Additional investigation is needed for silica gel regeneration.
- Analysis on PET distillates showed the possibility to follow a decarboxylation pathway for the
- synthesis of not-for-fuel products such as BTX
- Analysis of PET also suggested optimized routes to control detrimental properties of energy carriers
- such the acid number.
- Recommendation of use of distillates 1T and 2T:
 - 1T can be used blended with conventional gasoline in spark ignited engines in dilution ratio of 50%.
 - 2T can be used pure or blended with conventional diesel fuel (MGO, MDO) at any ratio in diesel engines

6 Conclusion – Pyrolysis on Marine Litter

6.1 MAKEEN

The role of MAKEEN Energy (ME) in the project was to perform low-temperature pyrolysis on the leftover plastics received from GEES, and to assess the produced MGO towards the ISO 8217-DMA standard to evaluate the quality. It is important to note that the quality and quantity of the liquid products highly depends on the chemical composition and quality of the input material.

The obtained liquids, the black solid fraction and the gas was assessed regarding uses to obtain circularity

6.1.1 Liquids

MGO was analyzed and it fulfilled 11 out of the 13 measured requirements from ISO 8217-DMA. The measured acid number was slightly higher than the upper limit, the viscosity measured at 40°C was slightly lower than the lower limit, while the results showed a higher amount of chlorine than what can be accepted for fossil based MGO.

The yield of the produced MGO after distillation was found to be 17.1% w/w, where the total amount of liquid produced constitutes of 63% w/w: The produced MGO is less

than 30% w/w of the total liquid yield, which together with the need for further posttreatments indicates that producing MGO from ML is not economically feasible. Another approach could be to keep the liquids in one fraction as pyrolysis oil. This can either be incorporated in the petroleum industry or be purified and used in the chemical industry as precursors to new plastic products or as solvents. Depending on which of the approaches is chosen, different certificates can be applied for, to visualize the environmental benefits of the product.

The naphtha was not analyzed, but it likely consists of short hydrocarbons with low boiling points. The uses of naphtha depend on the chemical composition, but it can be purified and used as a chemical feedstock to produce new plastic,

6.1.2 Gas

The chemical composition of the gas was monitored. The high content of small hydrocarbon chains makes the gas applicable for energy extraction. The best scenario is to utilize the gas into producing electricity to run the pyrolysis plant, which favors circularity of the gas and reduces electricity costs. Major obstacles for the technologies are varying gas compositions while energy and CO₂ taxes interferes with the business model making the solution less favorable. Instead, the low technology solution of a kettle can be used, which is a known technology in natural gas and biogas plants. This will not produce electricity, but the gas will be disposed, and heat extracted. Depending on the local boundary conditions the heat might be sold or added to the district heating network.

6.1.3 Solids

The black solid residue constitutes of 3% of the total product stream. It has not been analyzed, but previous analysis performed on black solid from the Plastcon project processing household sorted plastic waste showed that the black solid consisted of 40%-55% ash and 30%-50% carbon. Compared to Carbon Black, which the produced black solid visually resembles, the carbon content is higher in Carbon Black as this has a carbon content of more than 97%. A possible usage of the black solid could be as filler in asphalt for construction of roads.

6.1.4 Product validation

The production of MGO or pyrolysis oil from ML will not be able to compete economically with the fossil based MGO. With the collection of plastic from the ocean, the transportation, the energy consumption of pyrolysis, and the post-process refining steps, the MGO will be much more expensive to produce than the residue product from crude oil. On the contrary the ML based MGO or pyrolysis oil are environmentally beneficial and might be able to become certified according to

different green and environmental certificates. Depending on which of the approaches is chosen, different certificates can be applied for, to visualize the environmental benefits of the product.

6.2 SINTOL

Also, a subcontractor, SINTOL, performed tests on material supplied by GEES added PET bottles. The tests were performed in their marGnet prototype as batch processing. The output liquid was then distilled and polished.

From the mass balance it is evident that both film and epoxy resin are not good candidates for conversion. Solid residue was very high in both cases, and the amount of produced gas is more than half the product's yield for film.

Liquid product from epoxy contained large amount of water. Assessing the precise quantity of produced water was not possible since water/pyrolysis oil formed an emulsion which was not easily identified.

With respect to PET, liquid was composed almost entirely by water and actual oil yield was therefore still very. However, solid residue from PET might deserve better investigation but is out of the scope of this report.

The conclusions from batch-processing the different materials are:

- Only the foam feedstock showed an oil yield close to 50 wt% while both film and epoxy showed very low oil yield.
- Distillation revealed the presence of water-oil emulsion which breaks upon heating.
- Amount of water was significant affecting the distillation profile
- Liquid retention of silica gel was significant. Additional investigation is needed for silica gel regeneration.
- Analysis on PET distillates showed the possibility to follow a decarboxylation pathway for the synthesis of not-for-fuel products such as BTX.
- Analysis of PET also suggested optimized routes to control detrimental properties of energy carriers such the acid number.
- Recommendation of use of distillates:
 - The first fraction can be used blended with conventional gasoline in spark ignited engines in dilution ratio of 50%.
 - The second fraction (here washing and dilution with conventional diesel fuel was made to reduce the viscosity and the liquid retention of the sorbent)

can be used pure or blended with conventional diesel fuel (MGO, MDO) at any ratio in diesel engines

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